

How to install BioCAsE on Windows

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Disclaimer: This *How To* is written as a low-level step-by-step guide. Minor changes may occur due to different IT systems or management approaches. If you encounter any issues, please get in touch with your local IT support person.

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1. Background

The FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reproducible) principles [1] play an increasingly important role; a key component is to provide rich metadata. Currently, there is no metadata standard for farm animal research, and no specific repository exists for farm animal data, especially for phenotypic data. Phenotypic data are mostly uploaded to general-purpose repositories, such as [Zenodo](#) and [Dryad](#), which request metadata relevant for publications. Unfortunately, in the case of data publication, the actual characteristics of the data itself are not required [2, 3].

The situation is different in the biodiversity community. We have evaluated [Access to Biological Collection Data](#) (ABCD) standard [4] developed in the biodiversity community and the corresponding freely accessible [Biological Collection Access Services](#) (BioCAsE) [Provider Software](#) [5]. BioCAsE enables the publication of data using the ABCD data scheme. Moreover, BioCAsE is working under different operating systems (for an overview, see [Section 1.1](#)) and provides the following possibilities:

- Besides common SQL databases, it is possible to connect to EXCEL and MS Access files (only under Windows).
- Additionally, templates for mapping a specific database schema to the ABCD schema can be shared.

Conclusion: Instead of developing a standard for farm animals from scratch, it was assessed whether the ABCD standard supported by BioCAsE could be adapted for the purpose. We have therefore created this low-level step-by-step *How To* especially for Windows, which supplements the existing official documentation for installing [BioCAsE](#). This *How To* is more detailed than the official documentation and is suitable for less experienced users.

1.1 BioCAsE installation options

In this section, we provide a brief overview of BioCAsE installation options and present the advantages and disadvantages in Table 1 (see [BioCAsE Installation](#)).

Table 1: Overview of the various BioCAsE installation options

Operating system	Installation possibility	Advantages	Disadvantages
Linux	Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installing all components individually – maximal freedom • Potential to include packages for all potential databases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires some knowledge of Linux and installations • Regular updates individually required
	Docker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All in one solution with the environment in a container • Easy update 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some basic Docker knowledge is required

	Server	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It could be a regular or Docker installation with advantages and disadvantages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of server infrastructure and access management
Windows	Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It could be a local installation • No fear of accidentally submitting your data somewhere 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depending on knowledge and requirements, the installation could be difficult
	Docker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to install and update 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Docker is not primarily developed for Windows – Problems could occur, and it is currently not recommended • Connection with databases more complicated (except SQLite)
	Server	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is the possibility to use the Microsoft SQL Server (generally also possible as local installation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depending on the size of the database: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small database: e.g., a free version of the Microsoft® SQL Server® 2022 Express is available - Moderate or big database: Licensing prices need to be paid • Administration knowledge required

In general, the basis of the BioCAsE software is the programming language Python; therefore, Python must be installed independent of the operating system, except when the BioCAsE Docker is used. Furthermore, the main difference between the two operating systems lies in the potential usable databases. Regardless of the choice, it is always necessary for the user to have administrative rights. Issues occurred when testing BioCAsE Docker under Windows; we summarise these briefly in the next section. In general, we recommend performing a local installation under Windows, which is explained step-by-step in [Chapter 2](#).

1.2 Installing BioCAsE via Docker under Windows

BioCAsE is also provided as a Docker image, which simplifies the installation process and supports maintenance through updates. In general, Docker in combination with Linux systems is an optimal combination. In contrast, the combination of using Docker and Windows is currently not recommended based on the following reasons:

- Docker is not optimized for Windows. It has improved over the years, but depending on your system's settings and resources, the installation on Windows is not trivial.
- Another reason against using Docker is the latter application of BioCAsE, which requires a connection to a potential data source. Such a connection complicates the use of any database except [SQLite](#). To access specific Windows-based database management systems, such as MS

Access or Excel, you need the standard application programming interface, "Open Database Connectivity (ODBC)". The connection between the database and the ODBC must be established within the Docker container.

Both led to problems during the installation and the usability of BioCAsE. Hence, we recommend installing BioCAsE locally under Windows if no server is available. The instructions for installing BioCAsE locally are described in detail in the next chapter.

2. Installation under Windows

This chapter explains the local installation under Windows step by step. The installation was tested under Windows 10 Enterprise/Home (64-bit system) and Windows 11 Enterprise (64-bit system). Different installations were performed over time, within the *How To* the last tested BioCAsE version was 3.8.8 using the Python version 3.13.5. We recommend using this BioCAsE version or higher. Moreover, a list of databases that can be connected via BioCAsE can be found in [Appendix A.1](#).

2.1 Requirements and installation tests

Here, briefly, the requirements and installation tests are provided.

Requirements

- To follow the *How To*, the user must have administrative rights.
- To clarify, it is possible to install BioCAsE on a remote server, but this is not mandatory. If you already have a server / or an institutional server and background knowledge for administering a server, you can also apply this installation. However, you can also install BioCAsE on your local computer with a local web server.

Installation tests

This *How To* has been executed under Windows 10/11 enterprise/home on 64-bit operating system x64-based processor.

The last test was performed with BioCAsE version 3.8.8 and Python version 3.13.5 (Windows 11 Enterprise).

Previous tests:

BioCAsE versions: 3.8.4, 3.8.5 using Python version 3.11.6 (Windows 10)

3.8.7 using Python version 3.11.9 (Windows11)

Python: The latest working Python version is 3.11.9 together with BioCAsE version 3.8.7 (tested on June 2025 under Windows 11 enterprise). Higher Python versions will not work due to that [cglib – the traceback manager for CGI scripts](#) was removed from Python, which is needed by BioCAsE. We also discovered that the desired Python packages, which may be required depending on the planned

database to be used (see [Subsection 2.6.2](#)), caused problems during installation under Python version 12 (the last test happened in November 2023; see [Table 2](#) to see which Python packages worked). This issue was solved in the latest BioCAsE version 3.8.8.

General, a change from Windows 10 to Windows 11 does not have an impact on the software.

In general, updating to a newer BioCAsE version goes quick and easy (see [Updating BioCAsE Provider Software](#)).

2.2 Python

We recommend using [Python version 3.13.5](#) for the current BioCAsE version 3.8.8 (see [Installation tests](#)).

First, check if Python is installed on your local computer. An easy way to do this is to use the search function in the lower taskbar and type "python" in the Windows search bar. In the best case, you will see that Python is already installed, as shown in [Figure 1](#). You'll also notice that the version is provided directly, making it simple to check.

Figure 1: Screenshot shows the search for Python in the Windows search bar. The Python version is also visible, which in this case is 3.11.

If Python is already installed and the version number is ≥ 3.13 (recommended), then you can proceed to [Section 2.3](#); otherwise, perform the following:

1. Download the version for Windows: [Python 3.13](#), or select another version from the website [Download Python | Python.org](#)
2. After downloading, install Python by clicking on the downloaded ".exe" file. We recommend installing Python under "C:\Program Files", where administrator rights are necessary. The following illustrates each step of the installation process.
 - Tick "Use admin privileges when installing py.exe" and "Add python.exe to PATH" and click on "Customize installation" as shown in [Figure 2](#).

Figure 2: Screenshot showing which ticks need to be set and on what to click to proceed (red rectangle).

- Select all optional features as shown in [Figure 3](#) and click on the “next” button.

Figure 3: Screenshot showing which ticks should be set to enable optional features.

- Tick “Install Python 3.13 for all users” as shown in [Figure 4](#); activating this option also changes the path directly from “C:\Users\your_user_name\AppData\...” to “C:\Program Files\Python313”.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the recommended selection of the advanced options during the Python installation.

After successfully installing it, it is recommended to test Python.

- To do this, Python must be opened:

- It can be opened via the Windows search bar by typing “python” and double-clicking on the icon.
- Alternative, by using a general shell, for instance Windows PowerShell ([Figure 5](#)) or cmd, type "py" to start Python.
- To test Python, write "print("Hello World")" followed by an enter. The words “Hello World” will appear in the shell window.
- To close Python within the shell type “exit()” followed by an enter.

```

Windows PowerShell
Copyright (C) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

Try the new cross-platform PowerShell https://aka.ms/pscore6

PS C:\Users\melzer> py
Python 3.11.6 (tags/v3.11.6:8b6ee5b, Oct 2 2023, 14:57:12) [MSC v.1935 64 bit (AMD64)] on win32
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.
>>> print("Hello World")
Hello World
>>> exit()
PS C:\Users\melzer>

```

Figure 5: Screenshot of a successful Python test.

2.3 Local web server

A local web server¹ is necessary for successful usage of BioCAsE. Although [Apache](#) is one of the most popular open-source web server software, Windows includes [Internet Information Services](#) (IIS) to administer Microsoft's internal web server. In this *How To* we will only briefly focus on Apache and concentrate mainly on the Microsoft IIS Manager.

2.3.1 Apache

In general, Apache could be used as stated on the [BioCAsE wiki page](#). We did not test the installation of Apache, since the IIS Manager is already pre-installed on newer Windows operating systems. Based on that, we decided to go with the IIS Manager, believing it to be a simple, robust, and user-friendly solution under Windows for non-experienced users.

If you are interested in Apache as a web server, you can find more information on the following websites:

[Apache - Docs - Windows](#) (last accessed on June 2025)

[Apache for Windows 11: How to Download, Install & Configure](#) (last accessed on July 2025)

[Running Apache HTTPD Server on Windows 11 – Zhixian's Tech Blog](#) (last accessed on July 2025)

Download Apache: [Apachelounge - Download](#) (last accessed on July 2025)

¹ Additional note: With a local web server on your computer, only you can access it, as there is no automatic connection between this local web server to the internet and no possibility of accidentally uploading your data anywhere.

2.3.2 Internet Information Services (IIS) Manager

First, check whether IIS is already installed on the local computer. An easy way is to search for “IIS” in the Windows search bar.

Figure 6: Screenshot to check for the Internet Information Services (IIS) on the computer.

If IIS is already installed, the IIS Manager appears, as shown. In this case it is recommended to test if the web server works. Therefore, enter “<http://localhost>” in a browser and you should see the following on your screen as shown in [Figure 7](#). In the case it does not work, check the settings (see below), otherwise you can proceed directly to [Subsection 2.4](#).

The IIS Manager is typically pre-installed on your system. To activate IIS, follow these steps:

- Search for “Features” within the Windows search bar and click on “Turn Windows features on or off”.
- Activate “Internet Information Services” and the following sub-categories as shown in the screenshot.

- Activate in the subcategory “Web Management Tools” the following features.

- Activate in the subcategory “World Wide Web Services” the following sub-subcategories and features

- After activating, click on “OK”.
- Restart your computer

- Check if IIS is now available via the Windows search bar and check that it is working properly. Therefore, open a web browser of your choice and type in “<http://localhost>”. You should see the default front page of the IIS as shown in [Figure 7](#).

Figure 7: The start screen after successful Internet Information Services (IIS) activation

Potential problem: We have observed that it does not always work at the first activation. Hence, we recommend deactivating the IIS Manager and the Windows Process Activation Services (WAS). Perform the following steps (solution was found on [stackoverflow](https://stackoverflow.com) (last accessed on July 2025)):

- Search for “Features” in the Windows search bar and click on “Turn Windows features on or off”.
- Deactivate IIS Manager and WAS by removing the check mark.
- Restart the computer and activate both services again

2.4 Setup of BioCAsE

2.4.1 Download and extract the BioCAsE Software

Download the BioCAsE Provider Software archive from here [Releases biocase / bps GitLab](#). Be aware that you download a BioCAsE version $\geq 3.8.8$.

Unzip the archive to your preferred location. If you download the *.tar.gz you need to unpack it twice. First, the “.gz” archive, then the “.tar” should be unzipped. Finally, rename the resulting folder from “**bps-X.X.X**” to “**biocase**”. Please ensure that the folder containing the Provider Software is easily accessible for you and that you have administrator rights. We recommend choosing a destination on the “D:” drive, especially if your computer has separate “Windows” and “data” partitions. If this is not the case, you must place it in the “C:” drive folder.

More information on this can be found in the official documentation: [Installation - BioCAsE](#).

2.4.2 Install BioCAsE

Run the BioCAsE setup script by executing the setup.py file in the previously downloaded “biocase” folder. Then a window will automatically open and some text will appear about the installation, which you need to accept by pressing “Enter” ([Figure 8](#)).

```

C:\WINDOWS\py.exe
+++ BioCASE Provider Software
+++ Version 3.8.4
+++ Installer script

Configure BPS with:
Python      C:\Program Files\Python311\python.exe
BPS Library D:\biocase\lib

This setup tool adapts the BioCASE Provider Software (BPS) to your system environment.
You can cancel it by hitting Ctrl-Z + Return (Windows) or Ctrl-D (Linuxes).
Absolute path to installation in configuration set to D:\biocase.

Do you want to import the configuration of an older BPS installation (version 2.5+)? [no]

Please indicate the domain of your webserver: [http://localhost]
Please indicate the base URL you are planning to use for the software: [/biocase]
    
```

Figure 8: Screenshot showing the installer script for BioCASE with the three questions to answer.

Comments:

- Alternatively, the installation could be executed via shell, see [Appendix A.2](#).
- It is generally not advisable to modify the setup.py. Only use the question during installation, or use it after successful installation of BioCASE the Config Tool (see [Subsection 2.8](#)).

2.5 Linking IIS web server and BioCASE

For linking BioCASE with IIS and to provide the BioCASE web server via the default local host site, the following steps must be performed:

- Open the IIS manager and it should look like this.

- Expand under “Connections” (left side bar) the drop-down menu by using the arrow symbol. The two submenus “Application Pools” and “Sites” are displayed.

- Click the arrow next to “Sites” to expand the submenu. This will display the “Default Website” subsubcategory. Right-click on “Default Website” and select “Add Virtual Directory”.

- Provide an alias name (use “biocase”) as well as the physical path to the subfolder “www” in the biocase folder.

- After filling out, we recommend testing the settings by clicking the button “Test Settings ...”, and the popped-up window should show “Authentication” is Ok with a green checkmark. Close the “Test Connection” and agree to the naming by pushing the OK button.

- Under the Default Web Server term, a “biocase” folder will appear and you should click on it. Next, check that the index.html is active by clicking on the “Default Document” icon. In the right window bar, you see the corresponding “Actions” menu.

Then click under “Actions” on “Open Feature” and check if the file “index.html” is listed.

On the right-hand side, you can see that this file should be at the top of the list (see right top edge “Alerts”). To move this file, click on the file and on the right under “Actions”, you can move it up.

- Finally, two additional scripts for the handling have to be included. The Python CGIs (common gateway interface) have to be added to the BioCASE web server.
 - Click on the folder “biocase” and then on the icon “Handler Mappings” and select under “Actions” “Open Feature” (or double click on the icon).

- Click on the right side under “Actions”, “Add Script Map”.

- A window will pop up and two scripts need to be added:

First script: Fill out the blank fields as shown in [Figure 9](#). Please, pay attention that during selecting the “Executable“ to change from “.dll” to “.exe”. Moreover, pay attention that you add after the exe path the following “%s %s”.

Figure 9: Screenshot of setting up the “.cgi” script mapping.

Second script: Fill in as shown in [Figure 10](#). The only difference is that “*.py” instead of “*.cgi” is used, and another “Name” should be used.

Figure 10: Screenshot about setting up the “.py” script mapping

- Finally, we recommend to test the BioCASE web server as following:

Open a browser and type in: <http://localhost/biocase>

The opened webpage should look like this:

BioCASE Provider Software 3.8.4

Start

Welcome to the BioCASE provider software entrance page. This is BPS version 3.8.4.
Your BioCASE installation is up to date.

Documentation	Config Tool	Utilities	Query Tool	Report a Bug
Check the PyWrapper Wiki to find tutorials on installation, configuration, mapping, debugging, and other useful tips.	Configure new datasources, general options, the querytool, statistics, etc.	Several other utilities useful when managing your data provider software.	Query this datasource using a generic software that works with any database.	If you find a bug, please send us a short message.

DataSources

Each data source in a BioCASE service represent a database mapped to one or more conceptual schemas (like Darwin Core or ABCD). Click on its name to get more informaion about each of them and to access the data.

- [demo](#)

Powered by:

2.6 Required Python packages

Depending on the database types later used, additional Python packages need to be installed. For example, if you want to enable the Local Query Tool implemented in [BioCAsE](#). An overview of the potential package is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of the required Python packages depending on the used database, with information on which Python version was tested and which were not tested.

Package	Description	Command	Python version
SQLite3	Already pre-installed in Python; necessary for SQLite databases		
lxml	Necessary to enable the Local Query Tool (“a small portal for querying and browsing your BioCAsE webservice”)	<code>pip install lxml</code>	3.11.6, 3.11.9, 3.12.0, 3.13.5
pyodbc	To enable connection to Open Database Connectivity (ODBC), relevant for Excel and MS Access	<code>pip install pyodbc</code>	3.11.6, 3.11.9, 3.12.0, 3.13.5
psycopg2	Relevant for PostgreSQL database	<code>pip install psycopg2</code>	3.11.6, 3.11.9, 3.12.0, 3.13.5
MySQLdb	Necessary for MySQL database	<code>pip install mysqlclient</code>	3.11.6, 3.11.9, 3.13.5
fdb	Necessary for Firebird database	<code>pip install fdb</code>	Not tested
pymssql	Necessary for connect to Microsoft SQL Server	<code>pip install pymssql</code>	Not tested
cx_Oracle	Necessary for Oracle database	<code>pip install cx_Oracle</code>	Not tested
Sybase	SAP Sybase Data Connectivity		Not tested

In this *How To*, the focus only lies on selected database types (csv or txt, MySQL, PostgreSQL, EXCEL, MS Access) and how they can be connected to BioCAsE. The detailed instructions can be found in [Subsection 2.9](#). Therefore, only Python packages used in this *How To* have been installed. In addition, we also installed the lxml package to enable the realization of queries within the tool.

2.6.1 Install Python packages

Perform the following steps:

- To install a Python package under “C:\Program Files”, open a Shell as administrator as shown below, by right mouse clicking on the Shell program and selecting “Run as administrator”.

- Type in the newly opened window the command “pip install `python_package_name`”.

```
Administrator: Windows PowerShell (x86)
Windows PowerShell
Copyright (C) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

Try the new cross-platform PowerShell https://aka.ms/pscore6

PS C:\WINDOWS\system32> pip install psycogp2
Collecting psycogp2
  Downloading psycogp2-2.9.10-cp312-cp312-win_amd64.whl.metadata (5.0 kB)
  Downloading psycogp2-2.9.10-cp312-cp312-win_amd64.whl (1.2 MB)
----- 1.2/1.2 MB 14.5 MB/s eta 0:00:00
Installing collected packages: psycogp2
Successfully installed psycogp2-2.9.10
PS C:\WINDOWS\system32>
```

Problem:

If you have forgotten to run as an administrator or you do not have the write permission, then you can see it in the following output in the shell.

```
Windows PowerShell
Try the new cross-platform PowerShell https://aka.ms/pscore6

PS C:\Users\melzer> pip install lxml
Defaulting to user installation because normal site-packages is not writeable
Collecting lxml
  Using cached lxml-4.9.3-cp311-cp311-win_amd64.whl.metadata (3.9 kB)
  Using cached lxml-4.9.3-cp311-cp311-win_amd64.whl (3.8 MB)
Installing collected packages: lxml
Successfully installed lxml-4.9.3
PS C:\Users\melzer>
```

The default folder for the installed package is probably:

“C:\Users\your_user_name\AppData\Roaming\Python\Python313\site-packages”

To undo the installation there, delete the whole Folder “Python” (when you have no other Python version there, in this case, only the corresponding Python version) and run the install command again within a shell as administrator.

2.6.2 Check in BioCASE the installed Python packages

To check if the installation of the packages was successful, perform the following steps:

- Open a browser and open the [BioCASE web server](#)
- Click on “Utilities”

- Click on “Library test” (Library refers to packages or a collection of packages)

Providersoftware Utilities

Start » Utilities

In this page you can find several utilities useful when installing the software and for maintaining it. The first three links are used to check that you have correctly installed the provider software and you have correctly configured your webserver to run Python CGI scripts. In the description you can see what should you see after doing click if everything is fine.

Testing utilities

Utility	Description
Test your Python CGI installation	"Hello World" as CGI.
Library test	A CGI that looks for optional and required python libraries needed to run the wrapper. Here is an example installation at the BGDH.
PyWrapper query forms	Dynamic HTML forms to query any of your datasources with semi-automatically generated BioCASE protocol XML or SPICE queries to test the PyWrapper.

Other utilities

Utility	Description
Display your webservers environment	You will get a list of all environment variables set by your webserver as well as some custom calculations. If you have trouble with the BioCASE provider software attach this list to your error report to the BioCASE support.
Report a bug	If you find a bug, please send us a short message, preferably with some screenshots attached.

If you have problems, please refer to the [documentation](#) at the [PyWrapper wiki](#) or [contact us](#) by email.

- The library test checks if the libraries are installed and provides a color coding.

Python Library Tests

Start » Utilities » Test libraries

Python Interpreter: 3.11.6

green: Ok! | red: you have to install it | orange: install only if required

Libraries required for core wrapper

Library	Installed Version	Hint
BioCASE	3.8.4	Your BioCASE installation is up to date.

Libraries only needed for querytool

Library	Installed Version	Hint
lxml	4.9.3	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install lxml</code> .

Status of additional database dependent drivers

Library	Installed Version	Download Library
pyodbc	5.0.1	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install pyodbc</code> .
pymssql	not installed	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install pymssql</code> .
psycopy2	2.9.9 (dt dec pq3 ext lo64)	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install psycopy2</code> .
MySQLdb	2.2.0.final.0	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install mysqlclient</code> .
fdb	not installed	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install fdb</code> .
SQLite3	2.6.0	(integrated into Python)
cx_Oracle	not installed	Oracle module, you also need the Oracle Client
Sybase	not installed	Sybase module

📘 If you can't find the Windows installer package for your Python version, try your luck [here](#).

Optional external binaries

Binary	Status/Version	Path
Graphviz Dot	Binary not found	/usr/bin/dot
Java	Binary not found	java

Status of writable directories and files

Directory	Status	Path to problematic file
Configuration	Writeable	None
Log	Writeable	None
Archive temp dir	Writeable	None
Archive download Dir	Writeable	None

2.7 Additional optional software

2.7.1 Java

Java is only needed if you want to create [DarwinCore](#) archives with the BioCAsE software. In case you want to use only the [ABCD](#) XML standard, its installation is not necessary.

Java: <https://www.java.com/de/>

Downloading JAVA: <https://www.java.com/de/download/>

2.7.2 Graphviz

The Graphviz tool is quite useful for the visualisation of the database's structure and thus we would recommend installing it.

In this *How To* Graphviz package using the 64 bit system and Version 9.0.0 was used.

Download Graphviz: <https://graphviz.org/download/>

- Select a compatible installer and during the installation, make sure to tick “Add Graphviz to the system PATH for all users”

- Perform a restart of the computer.

- Check in BioCASE if Graphviz is found (green) using the library test (steps to get there see [Subsubsection 2.6.2](#)).

Python Library Tests

Start > Utilities > Test libraries

Python Interpreter: 3.11.6

green: OK! | red: you have to install it | orange: install only if required

Libraries required for core wrapper

Library	Installed Version	Hint
BioCASE	3.8.4	Your BioCASE installation is up to date.

Libraries only needed for querytool

Library	Installed Version	Hint
lxml	4.9.3	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install lxml</code> .

Status of additional database dependent drivers

Library	Installed Version	Download Library
pyodbc	5.0.1	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install pyodbc</code> .
pymssql	not installed	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install pymssql</code> .
psycopg2	2.9.5 (dt dec pq3 ext lo64)	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install psycopg2</code> .
MySQLdb	2.2.0.final.0	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install mysqlclient</code> .
fdb	not installed	Use PIP to install from PyPI: <code>pip install fdb</code> .
SQLite3	2.6.0	(integrated into Python)
cx_Oracle	not installed	Oracle module, you also need the Oracle Client
Sybase	not installed	Sybase module

 If you can't find the Windows installer package for your Python version, try your luck here.

Optional external binaries

Binary	Status/Version	Path
Graphviz Dot	9.0.0	/usr/bin/dot
Java	Binary not found	java

Status of writable directories and files

Directory	Status	Path to problematic file
Configuration	Writeable	None
Log	Writeable	None
Archive temp dir	Writeable	None
Archive download Dir	Writeable	None

Problem:

In the case that the Graphviz Dot is still orange (“Library not found”), then here are two potential solutions. One solution which includes to set the environment path within the environment variable to enable using Graphviz within the whole system, please see [Appendix A.3](#). The faster solution is to set the Graphviz path within BioCASE.

- Open BioCASE in a browser (or click: <http://localhost/biocase>)
- Click on “Config Tool”

BioCASE Provider Software 3.8.7

Start

Welcome to the BioCASE provider software entrance page. This is BPS version 3.8.7.

Your BioCASE installation is up to date.

Documentation	Config Tool	Utilities	Query Tool	Report a Bug
Check the PyWrapper Wiki to find tutorials on installation, configuration, mapping, debugging, and other useful tips.	Configure new datasources, general options, the querytool, statistics, etc.	Several other utilities useful when managing your data provider software.	Query this datasource using a generic software that works with any database.	If you find a bug, please send us a short message.

- Click on “System administration”

- Provide Graphviz path in line “Path to Graphviz executable (optional)” and confirm by clicking the update config button

2.8 Changing the default password and other settings

To modify settings, such as changing the default administrator password “ACDC”, follow these steps:

- Open BioCASE in a browser (or click: <http://localhost/biocase>)
- Click on “Config Tool”

- Click on “System administration”

- The server configuration screen is shown below, where you can change settings such as the administrator password. To change the administrator password, simply modify the “Admin password” field.

BioCASE Configuration Tool - System Administration

Home | Global configuration

Server Configuration

Webserver domain:	http://localhost
Base URL:	/biocase
Path to Graphviz executable (optional):	C:/Program Files/Graphviz/bin/
Admin password:	****
RecordResultLimit:	1000
Caching:	True
Debug logs:	True
Java binary:	C:/Program Files/Java/jre1.8.0_333/bin/java
Max memory usage for Java VM (MB):	4096
Sort buffer size for DarwinCore Archive transformation (number of rows):	500000
Archive expiration period in days (0=never):	0
Number of retries for XML archiving (0=none):	0
AnnoSys base URL (0=none):	https://annosys.bgbm.fu-berlin.de/AnnoSys

2.9 How to connect a database with BioCASE

There are a number of databases that can be connected with BioCASE (see list in [Appendix A.1](#)). Within this *How To*, we have tested the following: [csv or txt](#), [MySQL](#), [PostgreSQL](#), [EXCEL](#), [MS Access](#). For testing purposes, an empty database or Excel file is enough to establish a connection.

After a successful connection, in the next step, the underlying database structure needs to be provided in BioCase to perform an appropriate mapping, but this is beyond the scope of this *How To*. Please have a look at it. A detailed description can be found here: [DatasourceSetup - BioCASE Provider Software](#).

2.9.1 Connecting steps for all databases

To connect to a database, the following steps have to be performed independent of the type of database.

- Open BioCASE in a browser (or click: <http://localhost/biocase>)
- Click on “Config Tool”

- Click on “System administration”

BioCAsE Configuration Tool

Start » ConfigTool

Welcome to the BioCAsE configuration tool! With this tool you can configure the whole BioCAsE software or just one data source.
Your BioCAsE installation is up to date.

System administration **Datasource administration**

Configure the general system options and all datasources Configure one specific datasource, choose which one:

- demo

- Naming the datasource and then click the button “Create DSA”

BioCAsE Configuration Tool - System Administration

Home | Global configuration

Server Configuration

Webserver domain:	http://localhost
Base URL:	/biocase
Path to Graphviz executable (optional):	/usr/bin/dot
Admin password:	****
RecordResultLimit:	1000
Caching:	True
Debug logs:	False
Java binary:	java
Max memory usage for Java VM (MB):	1024
Sort buffer size for DarwinCore Archive transformation (number of rows):	100000
Archive expiration period in days (0=never):	0
Number of retries for XML archiving (0=none):	0
AnnoSys base URL (0=none):	https://annosys.bgbm.fu-berlin.de/AnnoSys

Update config

Datasources

Existing Sources

Remove	demo
--------	------

1. Name: test_postgres

Template: empty

2. Create DSA Create new datasource

- Click on the new created data source

Datasources

Existing Sources

Remove	demo
Remove	test_postgres

Name:

Template: empty

Create DSA Create new datasource

- Click on the tab “DB connection”

BioCAsE Configuration Tool - test_postgres

Home | Overview | Settings | **DB connection** | DB structure | Archiving & Filtered export | QueryForms | Help | Report a Bug

Database connection

The connection to the database is **No Connection**.
[Edit Connection parameters](#)

Database Structure

You have configured 0 table aliases.
[Edit DB structure](#)

Schemas

- Fill out the shown template for each database type. In this *How To*, we will focus on:
 - [csv or txt](#)
 - [MySQL](#)
 - [PostgreSQL](#)
 - [Excel](#)
 - [MS Access](#)

Comments:

The name of the data source should be logical, especially when several databases will be connected. Moreover, pay attention that the user's name must not contain a space.

2.9.2 csv or txt

For testing purposes, two folders: "database-txt" and "database-csv" were created. The "database-txt" folder contains the corresponding txt files (table1.txt, table2.txt), while the "database-csv" folder contains the corresponding csv files (table1.csv, table2.csv). The process for linking to both types of databases (txt and csv) using ODBC is the same and follows these steps:

- Search for "ODBC" in the Windows search bar and click on the appearing "ODBC Data Sources (64-bit)". The following window will open.

- Go to the tab "System DSN" and click on "Add" and select "Microsoft Access Text Driver" and click on finish.

- Provide the necessary information as shown below by writing a Data Source Name and untick “Use Current Directory” to enable directory selection and set the path to the folder on your system where the database folder (e.g., “database-csv”) is located, and then click on “Options”.

- In the options, choose accordingly *.csv (or *.txt) and also have a look at “Define Format...”, there you have the opportunity to set for example format-specific settings.

- When all relevant adjustment are made click “OK” and end the program with “OK”
- Go back to BioCASE and fill out the mask and press “Save” (see [Subsubsection 2.9.1](#))

2.9.3 MySQL

For test purposes, a [MySQL](#) database “testdb” from user “Jane Doe” was created using the graphical user interface tool [MySQL Workbench](#).

To install MySQL see [MySQL:: MySQL Installation Guide](#) and how to create a database using MySQL Workbench see [How to Create MySQL Database in Workbench {Create Tables & Add Data} \(phoenixnap.com\)](#).

Linking MySQL database with BioCASE:

- Go to BioCASE (see [Subsubsection 2.9.1](#)) and fill out the mask and press “Save”

The screenshot shows the 'BioCASE Configuration Tool - trainingDB_mysql' interface. The 'Database Connection' section is active, showing a status of 'OK'. The settings are as follows:

- DBMS:** 1. mysql (Selected from a dropdown menu. Below it is the text: 'Select the db_module you want to use to connect to your database.')
- Host:** localhost (Text input field. Below it is the text: 'The host of the database as an IP number; if you are connecting via ODBC you can leave it blank.')
- Database:** 2. testdb (Text input field. Below it is the text: 'The name of the database or the ODBC DSN name')
- User:** JaneDoe (Text input field)
- Password:** 3. [Redacted] (Text input field)
- Encoding:** latin_1 (Dropdown menu. Below it is the text: 'If you are using Access you can leave it as it is. For other databases you may have to specify the encoding of your database. For Western languages it will be probably "latin_1"')

At the bottom, there is a 'Save' button and a note: 4. 'Once you click in save you can see that the connection to the database is successful in the status. If is not OK then there is a problem either with the connection parameter or with the database module to connect to it.'

2.9.4 PostgreSQL

For test purposes, a PostgreSQL database “test_postgres” from user “Jane Doe” was created using the web-based tool [pgAdmin4](#).

To install PostgreSQL see [Install PostgreSQL \(postgresqltutorial.com\)](#) and how to create a database see [Connect to PostgreSQL Database \(postgresqltutorial.com\)](#) and [pgAdmin4 documentation](#).

Linking PostgreSQL database with BioCASE:

- Go to BioCASE (see [Subsubsection 2.9.1](#)) and fill out the mask and press “Save”

The screenshot shows the 'BioCASE Configuration Tool - test_postgres' interface. The 'Database Connection' section is active, showing a status of 'OK'. The settings are as follows:

- DBMS:** 1. psycopg2 (Selected from a dropdown menu. Below it is the text: 'Select the db_module you want to use to connect to your database.')
- Host:** localhost (Text input field. Below it is the text: 'The host of the database as an IP number; if you are connecting via ODBC you can leave it blank.')
- Database:** 2. test_postgres (Text input field. Below it is the text: 'The name of the database or the ODBC DSN name')
- User:** JaneDoe (Text input field)
- Password:** 3. [Redacted] (Text input field)
- Encoding:** latin_1 (Dropdown menu. Below it is the text: 'If you are using Access you can leave it as it is. For other databases you may have to specify the encoding of your database. For Western languages it will be probably "latin_1"')

At the bottom, there is a 'Save' button and a note: 4. 'Once you click in save you can see that the connection to the database is successful in the status. If is not OK then there is a problem either with the connection parameter or with the database module to connect to it.'

2.9.5 Excel

For test purposes, an empty test_excel.xlsx was created (analogue for *.xls, *.xlsm, *.xlsb).

Linking to the database with ODBC:

- Search for “ODBC” in the Windows search bar and click on the appearing “ODBC Data Sources (64-bit)”. The following window will open.

- Go to the tab “System DSN” and click on “Add” and select Microsoft Excel Driver and click on finish.

- Fill out the mask: provide “Data Source Name”, select “Version” for Excel, and click on “Select Workbook” to set the path to Excel Workbook.

- When all relevant adjustments are made, click “OK” and end the program with “OK”.
- Go back to BioCASE and fill out the mask and press “Save” (see [Subsubsection 2.9.1](#))

BioCASE Configuration Tool - test_excel

Home | Overview | Settings | **DB connection** | DB structure | Archiving & Filtered export | QueryForms | Help | Report a Bug

Database Connection

Status: **OK**

1. **DBMS**: odbc_excel
Select the db_module you want to use to connect to your database.

Host: localhost
The host of the database as an IP number; if you are connecting via ODBC you can leave it blank.

2. **Database**: test_excel
The name of the database or the ODBC DSN name.

User: root

Password: [Empty]

Encoding: latin_1
If you are using Access you can leave it as it is. For other databases you may have to specify the encoding of your database. For Western languages it will be probably "latin_1".

3. **Save**
Once you click in save you can see that the connection to the database is successful in the status. If is not OK then there is a problem either with the connection parameter or with the database module to connect to it.

Powered by: BioCASE

Comment:

In the case you see by the database connection, the status “No Connection” is in red. Check for typos and ensure that the corresponding **Excel sheet is closed**.

2.9.6 MS Access

Setup: For test purposes, an access database, named „test_access.mdb“ (all work analogue for *.accdb) was created.

Linking to the database with ODBC:

- Search for “ODBC” in the Windows search bar and click on “ODBC Data Sources (64-bit)”. The following window will open.

- Go to the tab “System DSN” and click on “Add” and select “Microsoft Access Driver”.

- Fill out the mask: provide “Data Source Name” and click on “Select” to provide the path to the database.

- After clicking “OK” and ending the program with “OK”
- Go back to BioCASE and fill out the mask and press “Save” (see [Subsubsection 2.9.1](#))

References

- [1] Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- [2] Melzer, S. Fischer, R. E. Jahnel, J. Holetschek, C. Kasper (2024) Is the ABCD standard appropriate for comprehensive metadata description for pig data? In: *Book of Abstracts of the 75th Annual Meeting of the European Federation of Animal Science*, p. 996, Florence, Italy (1-5 September 2024), ISBN: 979-12-210-6769-9, [2024 Florence EAAP Book Abstracts.pdf](#)
- [3] Larzul, C., Hurtaud, C., Melzer, N., Fischer, S., Kasper, C., de Koning, D., Boogaard, H., & Lokers, R. (2025). FAIR data guidelines for pig research. Zenodo.
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- [4] Holetschek J., Dröge G., Güntsch A. & Berendsohn W.G. 2012: The ABCD of primary biodiversity data access. *Plant Biosystems - An International Journal Dealing with all Aspects of Plant Biology: Official Journal of the Societa Botanica Italiana*, 146:4, 771-779,
<https://www.doi.org/10.1080/11263504.2012.740085>
- [5] FAIRsharing.org: BioCAsE; Biological Collection Access Service, FAIRsharing ID:
<https://fairsharing.org/4209>

Appendix

A.1 Database options for BioCAsE

Here is an overview of the possible databases which could be connected within BioCAsE.

Table A.1: Overview of the various BioCAsE connecting database options

Database connection in BioCAsE	Link to database provider	In How To	Last accessed
db2	db2		2025-09-12
firebird	firebirdsqli ; KinterbasDB		2025-09-12
mysql	MySQL	2.9.3 MySQL	2025-09-12
odbc	Microsoft-ODBC		2025-09-12
odbc_4d	4D ODBC DRIVER ; 4D MANUALS		2025-09-12
odbc_access	MS Access	2.9.6 MS Access	2025-09-12
odbc_db2	DB2 ODBC CLI driver Download - Installation		2025-09-12
odbc_excel	Excel ; ODBC-Excel	2.9.5 Excel	2025-09-12
odbc_filemaker	FileMaker		2025-09-12
odbc_firebird	Firebird		2025-09-12
odbc_foxpro	Foxpro		2025-09-12
odbc_text	Text	2.9.2 csv or txt	2025-09-12
odbc_tsq1	Transact-SQL (T-SQL) ; T-SQL info		2025-09-12
odbc_tsq1_2012+	Transact-SQL (T-SQL) ; T-SQL info		2025-09-12
oracle	Oracle		2025-09-12
oracle8	Oracle8		2025-09-12
pyscopg2	PostgreSQL ; Pyscopg for PostgreSQL database	2.9.4 PostgreSQL	2025-09-12
pymssql	pymssql		2025-09-12
pymysql_2012+	PyMySQL		2025-09-12
sqlite	SQLite		2025-09-12
sybase	Sybase		2025-09-12

Go back to [2. Running BioCAsE setup script](#)

Go back to [2.9 How to onnect a database with BioCAsE](#)

A.2 Running the setup script within a shell

Alternative way: Open a shell (Windows PowerShell, CMD, etc.) and navigate in the shell to the “biocase” folder.

- Exemplarily shown for Windows PowerShell


```
Windows PowerShell
Copyright (C) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

Try the new cross-platform PowerShell https://aka.ms/pscore6

PS C:\Users\melzer> cd D:\biocase\
PS D:\biocase>
```

- Exemplarily shown for CMD


```
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.19045.3636]
(c) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

C:\Users\melzer>D:
D:\>cd biocase
D:\biocase>
```

- Running the setup.py, just type the following: “py setup.py”

Go back to [2.4.2 Running BioCASE setup script](#)

A.3 Check and set environment path for Graphviz

In the case the Graphviz Dot is still not found (orange), please check the environment path as follows:

- Search for “advance” within the Windows search bar and click on “View advanced system settings”

- Click on the button “Environment Variables” and you should get the following information

- Check by “System variables”: select “Path” and click on Edit, and check if Graphviz is listed, if the path is missing, then please add the location. First click on “New” and then “Browse” and navigate to “C:\Program Files\Graphviz\bin”
- Perform a restart of your computer
- Check in BioCASE if Graphviz Dot is found (see [Subsubsection 2.7.2](#))

Go back to [2.7.2 Graphviz](#)